

EFFICIENT BUILDING MATERIALS AND METHODS OF BUILDING CONSTRUCTION

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Annotation: One of the main tasks of construction in modern Uzbekistan is to reduce its cost and increase energy efficiency. New economic conditions predetermine the peculiarities of the approach to the choice of efficient construction technologies, building materials, products and structures in the construction of buildings.

Key words: construction, building materials, modern technologies, construction of buildings.

Introduction. An analysis of the indicators of the competitiveness of materials shows that in order to solve the tasks set, it is necessary that the properties of the materials comprehensively satisfy the operational requirements imposed on them.

An analysis of the methods of erecting buildings and structural schemes that exist today shows [1] that the most effective and most fully satisfying modern architectural and construction requirements are monolithic and frame-monolithic structural systems for erecting buildings. That is why the foreign construction practice [2, 3] has almost completely switched from buildings with load-bearing walls made of small piece materials to frame-type buildings. The frame method allows you to separate the materials used for the construction of buildings into heat-insulating and structural. Structural materials (high-strength concrete of continuous structure) are used for the installation of columns, ceilings, stiffening diaphragms, etc. Non-load-bearing enclosing structures are made of heat-insulating materials,

which, with sufficient strength and weather resistance, effectively work as wall structures. Due to this specialization of materials, a reduction in material consumption and a comprehensive increase in the technical and economic efficiency of buildings are achieved.

Frame-monolithic buildings are erected using various formworks, which are divided into removable and non-removable. Most often in construction, collapsible small- or large-panel removable formwork is used [2, 7]. This technology of building construction has many advantages, but also a number of significant disadvantages. For example, when using it, it is necessary to take breaks during the work in order for the laid concrete to reach the stripping strength.

This leads to unproductive time losses, increased labor intensity due to the need to assemble the reinforcing cage in construction conditions, and the influence of atmospheric factors on the quality of construction work. In addition, reinforced concrete structures made of cast concretes transport sound and heat well, which does not meet modern requirements for the acoustic and thermal efficiency of buildings. These shortcomings have led to the fact that more and more experts are promoting the use in construction of a combination of removable and fixed types of formwork, or the use of only fixed ones. Practice shows that chip-cement, chipboard, cement-bonded chipboards [3, 5] and expanded polystyrene products [2, 6, 9] are currently used as fixed formwork elements. I believe that the technologies for erecting buildings using the listed materials as fixed formwork are not without drawbacks. And that's why. All listed types of fixed formwork must be protected from the effects of atmospheric influences (moisture and temperature). Due to their insufficient rigidity and tensile strength, it is impossible or inconvenient to attach elements of hinged engineering equipment to their surface, which any modern building is saturated with. It is not easy to carry out the laying of engineering communications before laying concrete in the formwork, but after the structural concrete has hardened, the possibility of repairing communications during operation is excluded.

There are restrictions on the number of storeys and the layout of buildings under construction. In addition, a material such as expanded polystyrene is characterized by combustibility, physical instability at temperatures above +550 C, and toxicity during the transition to the gas phase. Wood-cement slabs are waterproof, therefore, after laying the foam concrete mixture in them, they retain moisture not bound by cement for a long time, which does not allow the structure to acquire design thermal properties for a long time.

However, the use of fixed formwork in construction is very promising, since it helps to increase the speed of construction and minimize the mass of buildings; saving of rebar and cement; reducing dependence on atmospheric factors in the production of concrete works; simplifying the organization of work due to the ease of installation of prefabricated products and the refusal to use a number of types of lifting equipment; improvement of sound and heat insulation. A limiting factor in the development of promising methods of erecting buildings using fixed formwork is the shortcomings of the materials used, which consist in the lack of sufficient vapor permeability, insufficient weather resistance or chemical aggressiveness.

At present, the construction industry of Uzbekistan has mastered the technology of fiber foam concrete, cellular concrete characterized by high tensile strength, controlled permeability and high weather resistance [4, 10]. Therefore, I believe that the use of this material for the manufacture of fixed formwork elements can give a high technical and economic effect in construction, since its properties make it possible to eliminate a number of disadvantages that are typical for the construction of buildings in fixed formwork [11].

It is proposed to jointly use large-sized formwork products made of prefabricated fiber foam reinforced concrete and monolithic reinforced concrete frame structures of prefabricated production, mutually complementing each other. Reinforced concrete of a continuous structure will provide the building structure (ceilings, beams, columns) with the necessary bearing capacity, and reinforced concrete of a cellular structure, performing the function of sound and heat insulation,

will help to reduce the construction time of buildings, increase the strength of monolithic concrete, improve the fire-technical properties of the building, reduce costs for handling equipment, warehousing and interior decoration.

The properties of fiber foam concrete products used in the construction of a building object in fixed formwork provide smooth front surfaces of building structures. This eliminates the need for plastering and a number of special preparations for decorative finishing of facades and interiors of buildings. That is, labor-intensive "wet processes" that force to take into account seasonality and require the use of highly skilled manual labor fall out of the technological cycle of construction work. This method of construction of buildings will significantly reduce the time and cost of construction. The properties of walls made with the use of such formwork products make it possible to attach attachments to them and conveniently cut through the grooves for laying or repairing engineering communications.

Conclusions. Fixed formwork made of fiber foam concrete in combination with the range of already manufactured products will allow building buildings according to the following design schemes:

- with a supporting frame made of monolithic reinforced concrete;
- with load-bearing walls made of fiber foam concrete;
- with load-bearing monolithic reinforced concrete walls, made in the FPB formwork (stiffening diaphragms and elevator shafts are made in the same way);
- combined;
- with pitched roofs and attic floors.

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